

REIMAGINING CREATIVITY: LITERATURE IN THE DIGITAL AGE

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Abstract:

When a child is born, he knows no language but even at that tender age; he understands the emotions like love and anger. Language is not necessary to express our deep emotions but of course it adds value when we give words to our emotions. Literature is the mirror to society and now a days, society is much influenced from digital media. Digital Media includes e-books, social media as well as online-publishing (newspaper, magazines, graphics etc). Gone are the days when people wait for newspaper to reach at home and enjoy its reading with their morning cup of tea. Now with just single click on the mobile phone we have access to every digital platform and go through it without hesitation and wait. E-books means to store the text onto the internet rather than on paper. The concept of paperless work came into being during covid 19 pandemic when we all were cautious to spread covid from touch and it now has become a routine for all of us. From times immemorial we love to listen stories because they reflect our culture and entertain us. Social media is a recent way for such exposer where we quench our thirst of listening stories through different platforms. These stories create a real literature like our day-to-day lifestyle and impresses us. We cannot separate digital media and literature now as they are continuously complementing each other. At one level, digital media has simplified the creation of literature but at other level, it has disturbed the traditional concept of literature formation. Despite this fact, we cannot survive without digital media.

Keywords:

Digital Media, E-books, social media, Literature, Online-publishing.

Introduction:

Language is the medium to express our thoughts and literature is the way to express them. Digital media is a new platform to say whatever comes to mind openly or without hesitation. We are all living in the era of digital revolution which has totally influenced the creation of literature. New and latest technologies have changed the whole scenario of creativity and the way to create literature. There is strong need to re-examine the creative process for writing literature. The concept of creativity and its relationship with literary forms need to be reimagined. In this technological era, there is inter connectivity among literature, innovation, tool and terminology. Social media plays the key role for reshaping the task of imagination and help to showcase the talent in no time. Everyone is enjoying this new trend of writing which is in vogue now a days but actually this poses a serious problem for traditional style of creating literature. The clear inclination and love for digital media is apparently disrupting the conventional narratives.

Review of Literature:

When we go back the time, literature came into being in about 5th-11th century, it was not in print form. People used to sing about their culture in groups, a way to save the culture and tradition of a clan. This is known as oral literature which played an important role to spread information. The message given by the performers was always clear and had a moral lesson to the society. The invention of printing press in 15th century brought revolution in the history of written literature. People used to sit at a common place and read pamphlets, magazines and newspapers. With the spread of education among masses, awareness to read and write increased. Print media made it easy for the people to spend time in reading as it is having a physical form which gave more convenience as well as credibility. With fast changing world, print media replaced by electronic media. Television, Radio and Internet all these are covered under electronic media. Earlier, the electronic media mostly helped the business class but slowly and steady our dependency on this media increased as it easily connected the world together. This process of replacing one media by another continued and now the

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audio-visual form of literature is available known as digital media. Books are known as audio books, e-books, graphics and literature has many facets to share as blogs, podcast and websites etc. Internet is the major force behind all this. Technology efficacy is known to the world and everybody is getting influenced this mechanized way of evolution. Speedy and easy-going life is liked by all of us and social media is the best place to share where appreciation and criticism go hand in hand. This makes it comfortable as well as challenging. George Paul Landow (25 August, 1940-31May 2023) has the credit to develop in criticism and theory of electronic literature which needs digital devices to go through it. Generative Literature in 1950s, Interactive fiction in 1970s followed by hypertext fiction and digital poetry and so on. There is no dearth of accessibility of daily new editions of fresh terminology in this reference of literature which is of course available to read but cannot be obtained in the printed form. To name few, who gained recognition in this field includes Joseph Tabbi, an editor of Electronic Book Review and also known as former President of Electronic Literature Organisation, Scott Rettberg, an American Digital Artist, (Scott Rottenberg Biography, 2017) also known as the first executive director of Electronic Literature Organisation (History of Electronic Literature, 2017) and Nancy Katherine Hayles etc.

Digital media and literature:

William Hazlitt in his essay *ON THE IGNORANCE OF THE LEARNED* talked about bookworms, who are always indulged in reading books without paying any attention to people surrounding them. They keep sitting on their comfortable chair and continue reading the literature until they fall asleep and book automatically slips from their hand. Now, the scenario has been totally changed, books have been replaced by mobile phones and we have entrapped in the web of internet. In the present time, media has become an umbrella term for all the channels of communication and information whether social media, T.V. and internet. (Nair, 2020) Electronic literature is also an integral part of digital age as it started in as early as in 1950s with generative literature. On social media, people are reimagining creativity and new terminology and different forms of literature are being added up frequently but in 1950s, there was creation of poetry and fiction by using computers known as generative art. John Clark's Latin Verse

Machine (1830-1843) is probably the first example of mechanised generative literature while Christopher Strachey's love letter generator (1952) is the first digital example. In later part of the Twentieth century, hypertext fiction came into being which means to use hypertext links for creating and reading it.

Digital media has a broad range which became famous in 2010s and 2020s includes everything related to electronic media such as podcasts, TV, radio, website, social media, e-mail, SMS, blog, mobile Apps etc. Creativity is another name for literature. It can be a poem, story, novel, drama etc. But every bit of literature is the reflection of the society and the age in which it is written. With modernity in thoughts and progressive technology, expressions and expressiveness and expressor, all altered. Digital media is highly influential and wittingly giving new shape to our lives. Here, we are open to discuss our point of view and quickly able to get responses from our followers. When we think about literature, a book with graceful binding comes to our mind but in this digital world, books have been replaced by e-content and people are turning away from reading and they feel more comfortable to see an image or play within it, rather than creating an image via using well-crafted words. (Chatterjee,2019) Each one of us are interested in participating on social media to create new links for our benefit, listen praise and to get attention. Within few seconds, there comes a chance to become famous on social media. The influence of the content posted on social media depends on communicators, receivers, and contextual scenarios (Cheung & Thadani,2021). We cannot compare traditional style of writing with digitization of writing. With the passage of time, we all are bound to change. When the whole world is busy in posting daily something new and interesting posts, on different social media sites, writing about their love, liking, interests and even about their hatred, it's difficult to sit only as audience. We are bound to respond.

To spare much time to read a book of literature is not everybody's cup of tea as it requires patience and much needed love for reading literature. Today's generation is more inclined in reading short pieces of literature available on different platforms of media. Even they find it best place where they can pen down their emotions. Writing for media is like brewing instant coffee or tea as it holds no place for reflections and is

responsible only for conveying facts. (Nair, 2020). Among various digital media available, micro blogging sites are more famous for their literature content. Podcast, TV and radio have audio-video connections whereas Twitter, Facebook and Instagram are known for content creation. Twitter, an American social networking service which is operated by American company X Corp., help people to tweet on posts. Here, registered users can post images, type texts and upload videos. Users can like, retweet as well as comment on the post. Being established firstly in 2006, at present, this social networking site has approximately 335 million monthly active users worldwide (Stacy Jo Dixon, 2023). Twitter provides an artful and innovative platform for writing different genres like poetry and fiction etc. which is commonly known as Twitterature. 140-character limit was fixed earlier to write on it which is now been extended to 280 characters. It is a real challenge for creative writing. Well known and popular literary classics have been retold on Twitter in tweet format. The first published book entirely composed on Twitter was John Roderick(musician's) Electric Aphorisms which he composed in individual tweets between December 2008 and May 2009. (Nair, 2020) Chindu Sreedharan narrated the Mahabharata in 2628 tweets between July 2009 to October 2014 which was later published as a book by Harper Collins. Twitterature has its own value and impact now a days and Twitter novels are increasing in number day by day. Aphorism (a short saying requires interpretation), Haiku (short form of poetry that originated in Japan), Fan fiction (fictional writing but based on an existing work of fiction) are other different forms of literature known to be used on Twitter. To acknowledge the above information, it seems reasonable to conclude that sharing written work on social media is one such behaviour that has eradicated not only traditional forms of literature but literature altogether (Gorkhali & Chowdhury, 2022).

Instagram is well known for followers. Launched in October 2010 and now, owned by Meta Platforms, Instagram speedily gained popularity and has more than one billion active users at present. Such social sites enable all of us to be in touch with each other when we follow the same networking site. There are writers having millions of followers on Instagram and the most famous among them is Paulo Coelho having 2.2 million followers. The followers keep in touch with the authors through their Instagram

account where they upload videos and share their thoughts. It's very easy and informal way of keeping in touch with the followers. The genuine interest and attitude of the modern people particularly in the 21st century towards reading have changed... In 21st century novel has appeared in new version called micro fiction or flash fiction. (Kuntal D. Bompilwar, 2023)

Created in 2004 by Mark Zuckerberg with four other Harvard college students, Facebook is popular among every age group. The idea was to connect the Harvard university students but now it is open to all who is above 14 years. Users can create a profile by providing information about themselves. When they post text, photo or multimedia is shared with their friends on Facebook. Messenger directly connects all the users together. New notifications are received to reveal about your friends' post. Facebook gives an opportunity to make groups where people having similar beliefs can share and like content related to their nature. There are literary groups which provide assistance to the users not only in writing and publishing but also ginger up their papers. New writers get a chance to brush up their talent and established ones promote their work. Facebook is a vast medium to explore and improve writing. Facebook supports groups dealing with any genre and every genre. Aware audience, knowledgeable readers, and learned writers all have put their hands together for a better use of each media. In the same year 2004, Podcast, the term first time used by Ben Hammersley, a British Broadcaster is basically a digital audio or video file. This file can be downloaded from the internet and played on our own systems. It's true that literature and the way to present it is changing continuously and it is equally right when we say literature has lost its roots to grow differently. Lengthy novels, long dramas, beautiful and long poems etc have changed into short, smart and blunt pieces of literature. Modern literature has taken on a new shape due to technical developments and the proliferation of media outlets (Kumar, 2020). Daily, new works are being published on separate online social media sites and available for the readers and gives a glimpse to budding writers and fast responses make them famous within no time. This shows the influence of digital media that an unknown person of today can be a popular star of tomorrow. It is a continuous process and speedily changing with the passage of time. Digital humanity aims to

explore the merging of technology and humanistic inquiry within the domain of language and literature studies (Vanathi, 2023).

Conclusion:

It's evident from above discussion that digital media is a real challenge to traditional literature but at the same time a scope as its limitless and approachable to everyone. With the spread of Internet usage and computer revolution, literature writing in each genre has enhanced. Recently, emergence of Artificial Intelligence has overcome every possible way of creativity and it is assisting like a co-author in each form of literature writing. This is a grave concept to think over because it can handicap us by not letting us tax our brain which will definitely a big mistake on our part. So, we have to decide whether we need to work hard towards originality or give space to other tools to control us. Its necessary to walk with the flow but at the same time we should not sacrifice the originality in creativity.

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